

Emar: A Hittite Vassal in Late Bronze Age Syria

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Emar was a city-state in the Late Bronze Age from c. 1450 - 1200 BCE. Emar's religion provides an interesting scenario as we have a small corpus of unique rituals from the site. While there is little additional evidence concerning religion at Emar, the ritual corpus combined with a unique political situation warrants examination, even if such examination is brief due to a lack of evidence. Emar served as a Hittite vassal for at least the latter portion of its existence. The Hittites seem to have introduced a figure known as "the diviner" to oversee ritual and administrative tasks in the city. The vast majority of texts from Emar come from building M1, the so-called "house of the diviner," so the data is skewed. In addition, the political situation at Emar is unique to the ancient Near East in that the city elders appear to have been the primary ruling body of the city, even ahead of the king. Emar falls at the end of the Late Bronze Age along with many other civilizations in the region. The evidence we have today was recovered in a series of salvage excavations before the site was primarily covered by the waters of Lake Assad.

Date Range: 1400 BCE - 1200 BCE

Region: Emar

Region tags: Middle East, Mesopotamia

Emar, on the banks of the Euphrates. Note some parts of the site are currently beneath the water of Lake Assad.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Daniel Fleming, "Time at Emar."
- Source 2: Daniel Fleming, "The Installation of Baal's High Priestess at Emar."
- Source 3: John T. Thames, "The Politics of Ritual Change: The Zukru Festival in the Political History of Late Bronze Age Emar."

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://sites.google.com/view/forging-an-empire/home?authuser=0>
- Source 1 Description: Contextualizing Emar in its role as a Hittite vassal.

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– No

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– Yes

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Notes: Emar is in contact with the broader Hittite, Mesopotamian, and Levantine religious traditions of the Late Bronze Age, and, perhaps, even Egyptian ones. They are under Hittite control for most of their Late Bronze Age existence and the Hittites were extremely accommodating to other religious traditions, even adapting other gods and traditions for their use.

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

↳ Are the priests paid by polity:

– Yes

Notes: The diviner is the overseer of religious/ritual at Emar and is an official of the Hittites.

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

– Yes

Notes: Temple building and maintenance is commonly supported by the polity in the ancient Near East.

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– No

Notes: The king of Emar holds a minimal role in religion from the extant evidence. The diviner may serve as the "head of the religion" (anachronistic) and as a representative of the Hittite king.

↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

– Yes

Notes: e.g., the diviner

↳ Is religious observance enforced by the polity:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Polity legal code is roughly coterminous with religious code:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Polity provides preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax, exemption)

– Field doesn't know

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region)

population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– No

Notes: We do not have "religious texts" from Emar in the traditional sense. Our "religious texts" all pertain to ritual.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Notes: The religious architecture present is in the form of traditional Levantine tripartite temples which are not very large.

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Is iconography present:

– Yes

Notes: We find evidence for this in the ritual texts, particularly the 7-year zukru festival which notes the central focus of a statue of Dagan.

Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– Field doesn't know

Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Field doesn't know

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Field doesn't know

Belief in afterlife:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The answer is most likely "yes" based on similarities to other religions of the era and region which contain netherworld conceptions.

Reincarnation in this world:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Almost assuredly "no."

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Field doesn't know

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– Field doesn't know

Are grave goods present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The answer is, likely, "yes."

Are formal burials present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The answer is likely "yes."

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The answer is likely "yes" with this deity being the well-known Syrian god, Dagan.

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Likely "yes."

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Likely "yes."

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Likely "no."

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Likely "yes" but perhaps not punishment as we would conceive of it today, i.e., for societal wrongdoings.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Likely "yes," but not how we think of it today.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Likely "yes" as the religious group is basically equal to the population and government so governmental rules would equal religious rules in a sense.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– Yes

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Field doesn't know

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Yes

Notes: The "diviner" is in charge of overseeing ritual performance.

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Yes

Notes: The "diviner" oversees this.

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– Field doesn't know

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– Other [specify in comments]

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: City-state which is a Hittite vassal.

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Probably as an arm of the state.

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Probably the state but they are connected.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Field doesn't know

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Field doesn't know

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– No

Notes: Elites would have access to education.

Is such education open to both males and females:

– Field doesn't know

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: They are too interconnected with the state to separate them.

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: The diviner and the school of the diviner.

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: The Hittite state and local Emar ruling classes of the king and the city elders.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Probably as sacrifices would have been offered at the temples and food would have been distributed from the temple.

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Too interconnected with the state to separate them.

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The state most likely.

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Field doesn't know

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– Field doesn't know

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Field doesn't know

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– Field doesn't know

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: They may be in the Hittite military.

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The Hittite military.

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– Yes

Is use of this distinct written language confined to religious professionals:

– No

Notes: Not a "language" per say, but the script used by the diviner differs from the local cuneiform script. Both are Akkadian.

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Cuneiform Akkadian (Hittite, Hurrian, and Sumerian also appear at Emar).

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: See above.

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: See, D. Fleming, "Time at Emar."

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: They probably also operate on the Hittite calendar as well as other calendars from Mesopotamia.

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Field doesn't know

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know